

ISic0242

I.Sicily inscription 0242

Language

Latin

Type

unknown

Material

stone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy**Last Change**

2020-12-16 - Jonathan Prag edited the file from publications

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

First recorded by Mommsen in CIL (1883) as being in the Termini civic museum

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, unknown

Physical Description

A fragment seemingly broken on all sides

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

remains of two lines of latin text, both ends lost

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Latin capitals; in line 1 what is presumably a letter A is missing the cross-bar in Mommsen's representation in CIL

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. [---]SAΛI[---]

2. [---]VST[---]

Apparatus

Text after CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285329

EDR 127456

EDCS 22100570

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7451 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 169

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